

TEACHER'S GENERATIONAL COHORT AND SCHOOL HEAD'S PATH-GOAL LEADERSHIP STYLE: IMPACT ON TEACHERS' SELF-EFFICACY AND WORK ENGAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

School is a diverse organization that encompasses age, gender, ethnicity, and many other qualities. Seemingly, the generational cohorts of the teachers pose a significant challenge to the leadership of school managers on how to address conflicts for a healthy working environment. A study was conducted to discover the existing teachers' generational cohort and school head's path-goal leadership style and their impact on the teachers' self-efficacy and work engagement in the selected schools in the Division of Quezon Province, AY 2020-2021. The study utilized the descriptive correlational design and survey questionnaires for 217 teachers and 15 school-heads. The findings reveal that the teacher respondents belong to Generation Y while the school heads belong to Generation X. School heads demonstrated all the path-goal leadership styles with supportive leadership as the least. There was a significant difference in the teachers' and school heads' perceptions on the supportive and achievement-oriented leadership style but with small to medium difference. Self-efficacy and work engagement levels were very high among the teacher respondents. Supportive leadership style was the highest correlated leadership style in all dimensions of self-efficacy and work engagement. School heads and principals may utilize the path-goal supportive leadership style to increase the teachers' self-efficacy and work engagement.

Keywords: generational cohort, path-goal leadership style, self-efficacy, work engagement, supportive leadership